

Research data retention and disposal

An implementation project for the Institutional Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

Curtin University

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About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

Our project aimed to develop a process to manage research data retention and disposal based on the recommendations set out in the [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#) Retention and Disposal element. The project team included representatives from Curtin Information Management and Archives, Curtin Library, Digital and Technology Solutions, and Research Office at Curtin. The following summarises how the project interpreted and validated the framework recommendations.

Project Recommendation 1: Adopt data standards and identifiers that link researchers and research projects

We attempted to draft a comprehensive list of metadata required for research data retention and disposal. During this exercise it became apparent that information already exists in various research management processes, including the data management planning (DMP) tool, research management system, and the ethics application system. However, the information is often not captured in a machine-readable, structured manner. For example, various data description metadata elements are captured in one open-ended question in the DMP Tool. In order to reduce manual data entry, the Curtin DMP Tool will need to be redesigned. The team has also identified information that might need to be collected (or revised) upon research project completion. For example, whether the data has been published openly, and future application of the data.

ORCID is the main persistent identifier that has received institutional-level support across Curtin. ORCID integration is implemented in the university publication management system, Elements, but not with other internal systems. DOIs are minted for datasets and grey literature published openly by the Library. As we developed the retention and disposal data collection and decision workflow, along with the metadata requirement listing, we identified how RAiD, ROR, DOI and ORCID can be used to enhance data collection, data integrity and user experience.

Project Recommendation 2: Design integration tools for administrative and research management systems

When considering a retention and disposal workflow, we explored two options: (1) redesign the DMP Tool and (2) develop a new standalone research data register. Either option will require improved system integration. Redesigning the DMP Tool was preferred as this is a system that researchers are familiar with, and it could also encourage researchers to continue to update their DMPs throughout the research lifecycle. It is acknowledged that not all research projects have a DMP, but as of July 2022, Curtin researchers have created 10,861 DMPs and over 3,900 projects have been allocated space in the University research data storage (R drive). This approach is an appropriate first step. By connecting the

relation between the DMP to the data retention process, there is also an opportunity for the university to capture inactive data that is not stored in the R drive during the active phase of a project.

Curtin's research data storage is being migrated to the cloud (AWS). Files are automatically moved to various storage tiers (frequent access tier, infrequent access tier and glacier instant retrieval tier) depending on how frequently they are accessed. It was decided that in moving inactive data to the read-only deep archive tier, researchers need to initiate a workflow. The rationale for a non-automated process is so that Information Management & Archives staff can review the metadata and data to ensure they are adequately prepared for long term retention. It was noted that a data and database preservation strategy needs to be developed as well, in particular for research data that requires long term retention.

Recommendation 3: Develop a broadly applicable decision-making tool (matrix, decision tree, rubric) that can accommodate local policy

In Western Australia, the retention period for research data should begin upon project completion or publication. However, it is difficult to determine when a research project is completed through existing processes. It was decided that the financial closeout process could be used to trigger a prompt for researchers to consider whether the research project is completed and the research data has therefore become inactive. If so, the researcher will complete the data archiving section in the DMP to trigger the data archiving process. Development work to integrate various systems is required in order for this approach to work seamlessly.

We would welcome the development of a generic (cross-institution) decision-making tool to validate our proposed approach.

Recommendation 4: Ensure contemporary capture and propagation of metadata for research projects

While it is ideal to collect as much metadata as possible in the early stage of research, we identified metadata to be collected at the end of a project. In addition to metadata collection, PID implementation, system integration and potential automated workflows, considerations on data preservation are also vital. Curtin does not have a digital preservation procedure at this time. The project team produced a guidance document that includes recommendations for researchers on how to prepare their inactive data for archiving.

Resulting Improvements

Curtin University has a mature research data infrastructure. With the rapid increase of research data in storage, a key challenge to research data management at an institutional level is to identify what research data should be kept, how it can be efficiently stored and safeguarded, and what can be destroyed in accordance with legislation and policy.

This project coincided with the Curtin Digital Platform project. Part of it was to migrate Curtin's research data storage from on-premise to the cloud (AWS). The work and discussions as a result of this project have prepared internal stakeholders to consider how we can leverage the functionality and opportunities of AWS to improve the Curtin RDM infrastructure based on best practices.

Next Steps

The project demonstrated that a more robust and integrated end-to-end RDM infrastructure that can cater for the need of research data retention, disposal and appraisal is required. It was agreed that a discussion paper will be drafted to continue the work and conversations with stakeholders and researchers.

Project Outputs

Reusable outputs produced include:

- Metadata requirements for retention and disposal: version 1.0 of the metadata requirements has been made openly available for community feedback. Metadata elements are grouped by data description, governance, access, retention, appraisal, preservation, and sharing.
- Research data retention and disposal workflow: The diagram provides an overview of how a retention and disposal metadata collection and decision workflow can work at Curtin in the short term. It includes recommendations for researchers on how to prepare their inactive data for archiving.

Chan, J., & Dianne, J. (2022). Research data retention and disposal process and metadata requirements. Curtin University. <https://doi.org/10.25917/EDCN-5788>

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